

Corona Smoking Bucket

Essay

Map

Network

Corona Smoking Bucket

This 'Corona Smoking Bucket' was collected for The Wadjemup Museum on Rottnest Island in March 2020.

In late March 2020 the global pandemic of Covid19 virus – a form of the novel Corona virus – was being introduced to Australia by overseas travellers. Cruise ships were a particular concern following the Ruby Princess travellers having tragically spread the virus in eastern Australia and Tasmania. The Western Australia government suspended tourist operations on Rottnest Island (Wadjemup) to support the government response to the pandemic. Australian citizens aboard the Vasco de Gama cruise ship were directed to be quarantined on the island from Monday 30th March.

On 26 March 2020, Whadjuk monitors Ben Ugle and Brendan Moore were on the island to support conservation works on the Quod – a central part of the island's heritage precinct. The Quod is an extremely significant heritage location, being at the heart of the colonial prison precinct that operated to incarcerate Aboriginal men and children from 1838-1904, followed by a forced labour camp continuing until 1931. Aboriginal men from across Western Australia were made prisoners for simply responding to the loss of their land and to the impacts on Aboriginal society due to colonialism. Over 4000 prisoners were transported to the island prison; 370 men died on the island where they are buried in unmarked graves. The Quod served as prisoner accommodation until, in 1911, it was converted into holiday accommodation for tourists. Since the early 20th century the use of the island for recreation has largely obscured its significant traumatic Aboriginal history. Today Whadjuk Noongar people are recognised as the Traditional Owners of the island and are working with the Rottnest Island Authority on a project to appropriately recognise the history of the Quod and the Burial Ground.

On the morning of March 26th the two Whadjuk men chose to perform a smoking ceremony in the heritage common to bless the Quod works, the Island during the transition to pandemic quarantine facility, and the travellers who were to be quarantined there. Smoking ceremonies are often

conducted to cleanse a place spiritually, to welcome people, and as a sign of respect to people including past elders. Robert Smithson (Infrastructure Project Manager, Rottnest Island Authority) assisted the ceremony by providing a metal tin for the smoking. Given the unplanned nature of the event, the only suitable vessel he could find was a 'Corona' beer bucket.

Word Count: 391

Author Alistair Paterson

References:

Suggested citation: Alistair Paterson, *Corona Smoking Bucket*, in *Collecting the West: "99 Collections That Made Western Australia"*, 2021. (api.nodegoat.collectingthewest.net/ngSp5A859TB68Efn8S1ji)

Collecting the West is an Australian Research Council funded project: LP160100078

